

NOTES

Complexes of β -Isatin-4,4-dimethyl-3-thiosemicarbazone with some Bivalent Metal Ions

R. N. PAIHAKE

Chemistry Department, Tata College, Chaibasa-833 202
and

L. K. MISHRA*

Chemistry Department, Patna University, Patna-800 005

Manuscript received 27 November 1986, revised 9 December 1987,
accepted 24 December 1987

THE present paper describes the preparation and characterisation of complexes of Ni^{II} , Co^{II} , Cu^{II} , Mn^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Hg^{II} , Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} with β -isatin-4,4-dimethyl-3-thiosemicarbazone (1).

1

Experimental

Preparation of ligand: β -Isatin-4,4-dimethyl-3-thiosemicarbazone was prepared by condensing 4,4-dimethyl-3-thiosemicarbazide with isatin in hot methanol in presence of a little anhydrous sodium acetate¹, m.p. 222° (lit. 221°) (Found: N, 22.49. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4\text{OS}$ requires: N, 22.58%).

Preparation of metal complexes: The ligand H_2L (~0.01 mol) dissolved in hot methanol (50–60 ml) was added to a methanolic solution of the appropriate metal acetate in stoichiometric proportion. pH of the resulting solution was raised by adding methanolic solution of sodium acetate (3.0 g in 20–25 ml). The reaction mixture was stirred thoroughly and warmed on a steam-bath when a coloured complex separated gradually. It was filtered, washed with methanol and dried (CaCl_2).

For the preparation of Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} complexes an aqueous solution of the metal(II) chloride (0.5 g in 50 ml) was treated with aqueous pyridine (3–4 ml) and warmed to get a clear solution. The resulting solution was refluxed with a hot methanolic solution of the ligand in 1:2 molar ratio on a steam-bath when fine granular precipitates separated almost quantitatively. The products were filtered, washed with aqueous methanol and dried (CaCl_2).

Analytical and magnetic data of the compounds are recorded in Table I. The reflectance and ir (KBr) spectra of the complexes were recorded at I.I.T., Delhi.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND MAGNETIC DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		μ_{eff}^{**} (B.M.)
		Metal	N	
$\text{Ni}(\text{HL})_2$	Deep brown	10.82 (10.63)	20.14 (20.25)	3.57
$\text{Co}(\text{HL})_2$	Deep brown	10.58 (10.67)	19.93 (20.15)	2.96
$\text{Mn}(\text{HL})_2$	Deep brown	10.28 (10.01)	20.31 (20.40)	6.12
$\text{Zn}(\text{HL})_2$	Orange red	11.55 (11.69)	20.95 (20.94)	Dia.
$\text{Cd}(\text{HL})_2$	Orange yellow	19.01 (18.48)	18.40 (18.46)	Dia.
$\text{Pd}(\text{HL})_2$	Red	17.76 (17.57)	18.84 (18.67)	Dia.
$\text{Pt}(\text{HL})_2$	Orange red	29.69 (29.48)	12.48 (12.70)	Dia.
$\text{CuL}_2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Dark brown	20.01 (19.34)	16.98 (17.04)	2.14
$\text{HgL}_2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Red	42.60 (43.08)	11.95 (12.02)	Dia.

* $\text{H}_2\text{L} = \text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4\text{OS}$.

**At 304 K.

Results and Discussion

The complexes are practically insoluble in water but slightly soluble in ethanol, dioxan and benzene and soluble in DMF. The DMF solutions of the complexes are almost non-conducting ($\Lambda_{\infty} = 5-10 \Omega^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$ at 30°) supporting their non-ionic character. The copper complex $\text{CuL}_2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ does not lose water molecule below 100° indicating that the water molecule is either coordinated or strongly held in the crystal lattice. In case of the mercury complex $\text{HgL}_2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, the water molecule was lost gradually at 60–70° suggesting that H_2O is loosely held up in the crystal lattice. As expected Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Hg^{II} , Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} complexes were diamagnetic. The room temperature magnetic moment values of Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} and Mn^{II} complexes occur in the range of spin-free octahedral complexes². Magnetic moment value ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 2.96$ B.M.) of $\text{Co}(\text{HL})_2$ appears to be anomalous^{3,4}. In the reflectance spectra of $\text{Ni}(\text{HL})_2$ complex, a broad and medium band at 10420 cm^{-1} was assigned to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g} (\nu_1)$ transition. The value of Racah parameter (B) and β were found to be 916 cm^{-1} and 0.88, respectively⁵. The reflectance band located at 20830 and 17540 cm^{-1} in case of $\text{Co}(\text{HL})_2$ were assigned to ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g} (P)$ and ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}$ transitions, respectively in octahedral field⁶. The reflectance bands observed at 26315 sh ,

20 830m and 14 705w cm^{-1} in $\text{Mn}(\text{HL})_2$ and attributed to ${}^5A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ (G) and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ (G) transitions, respectively, in an octahedral field⁸. The electronic bands of $\text{CuL.H}_2\text{O}$ observed at 21 740m and 15 150m cm^{-1} were assigned to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1E_g$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ transitions, respectively, in tetragonal field. Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} complexes display one ligand field transition at $\sim 23\,200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ attributed to ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g}$ transition similar to planar complexes⁷. The second transition observed in the uv region at $27\,020\text{ cm}^{-1}$ was attributed to ligand absorption.

The ir spectra of the ligand display ν_{NH} at $3\,140$ (isatin NH) and $3\,040\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (thioamide NH). In $\text{M}(\text{LH})_2$ complexes, the former is retained while the latter disappears indicating deprotonation of the thioamide (HNCS) moiety. In case of $\text{ML.H}_2\text{O}$ complexes, both the NH vibrations disappear suggesting the deprotonation of both the NH moieties due to complexation. A broad band at $3\,450\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the aquo-complexes was attributed to ν_{OH} of water molecule. The $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ of the free ligand was observed at $1\,700\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which shifted to lower frequency by $38-50\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in $\text{M}(\text{HL})_2$ and $\text{HgL.H}_2\text{O}$ complexes but it remained unaffected in Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} complexes. The shift of $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ to lower stretch suggest coordination of C=O oxygen to metal. In case of Cu^{II} complex, the $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ almost disappears and a new $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ band observed at $1\,260\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicate that the C=O oxygen was coordinated to Cu by deprotonation in the enolic tautomer,

In case of the complex $\text{HgL.H}_2\text{O}$, the $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ band was observed at $1\,662\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating that the C=O oxygen being bonded to Hg^{II} in keto form and the disappearance of the isatin ν_{NH} suggest the coordination of isatin (NH) nitrogen to Hg^{II} through deprotonation. The deprotonation and involvement of the isatin part (NH) atom indicated the dimeric or polymeric nature of the complex. The aldimine (C=N) stretch of the ligand ($1\,630\text{ cm}^{-1}$) shifted to lower frequencies in almost all the complexes suggesting the involvement of C=N nitrogen in bonding with the metal atom¹⁰. The thioamide bands I, II and III of the ligand located at $1\,542$, $1\,356$ and $1\,140\text{ cm}^{-1}$ shifted to higher frequencies, while the thioamide band IV (890 cm^{-1}) shifted to lower frequency in the complexes by 200 cm^{-1} , indicating the bonding of deprotonated thiol (SH) in almost all the metal complexes^{8,9}. The new bands observed in the far-ir region $640-605$, $470-434$ and $420-335\text{ cm}^{-1}$ of the complexes were tentatively assigned to M-O, M-N and M-S stretches, respectively¹⁰⁻¹². Thus on the basis of the foregoing discussion it is inferred that the ligand offered

terdentate (O, N, S) chelation to Ni^{II} , Mn^{II} , Cu^{II} , Co^{II} and Hg^{II} while bidentate (N, S) chelation in Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} in the complexes. In case of Hg^{II} complex, isatin part (NH) is also involved in bonding and completing the coordination number four to Hg^{II} .

Acknowledgement

The authors are indebted to Prof. N. K. Jha of the I.I.T., Delhi for the reflectance and ir spectra.

References

1. D. J. BAUER and P. W. SADER, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1966, 65, 2224.
2. B. N. FIGGIS and R. S. NYHOLM, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, 6, 37.
3. R. L. CARLIN, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1965, 1, 1.
4. R. C. STOUFER, D. W. SMITH, E. A. OLVENGER and T. E. NORRIS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, 5, 1167.
5. C. J. BALLHAUSEN, "Introduction to ligand Field Theory", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1962, p. 268.
6. J. FERGUSON and D. O. WEST, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 278.
7. W. R. MASON and H. B. GRAY, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 90, 5721.
8. I. SUZUKI, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1962, 35, 1286, 1449, 1456.
9. G. R. BURNS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1977, 39, 1797.
10. S. J. GROBER, O. M. HARRIS and E. SINN, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1968, 30, 1805.
11. D. M. ADAMS, "Metal-Ligand and Related Vibrations" E. Arnold Publication, London, 1967.
12. M. GOLDSTEIN and W. D. UNSWORTH, *Inorg. Chem. Acta*, 1970, 4, 842.

Complex Formation with some Bidentate Ligands. Part-II. Stability Constants of Complexes of *vic*-Hydroxyaldoximes with Manganese(II), Cobalt(II) and Zinc(II)

C. K. BHASKARE* and P. P. HANKARE

Department of Chemistry, Shivaji University, Kolhapur-416 001 and

R. S. RAMPURE

Department of Chemistry, Sangameshwar College, Solapur-413 001

Manuscript received 20 June 1986, revised 2 November 1987, accepted 11 December 1987

In this paper we report the deprotonation constants of oximes of substituted-salicylaldehydes and formation constants of their complexes with Mn^{II} , Co^{II} and Zn^{II} in water-ethanol (50%, v/v) medium.

Experimental

Salicylaldoxime (SAO; AnalaR) was used as such. Other *vic*-hydroxyaldehydes were prepared by standard procedures^{1,2}. 3-Methylsalicylaldoxime (3-MSAO), 5-methylsalicylaldoxime (5-MSAO) and